

THE ROLE OF INTERNET COMMUNICATION IN SHAPING LANGUAGE IN AMERICANAH

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of Information Communication Technology (ICT) has reshaped human communication and influenced literary expression. Despite the richness of internet-mediated language and style, there is limited scholarly attention on their linguistic features and literary relevance. This study investigates the use of internet-mediated language and stylistic devices in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's Americanah. Adopting the Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC) framework, which differentiates between synchronous modes (telephone conversations, instant messaging) and asynchronous modes (e-mails, blogs, text messages), the study examines how these forms are employed in the novel. Using judgemental sampling, Americanah was selected as the primary source, complemented by secondary data from journals, textbooks, dissertations, and other relevant literature. Data were analyzed by identifying and classifying internet-mediated features into blogs, e-mails, text messages, and telephone conversations. The findings reveal that internet-mediated communication (IMC) enhances narrative efficiency and immediacy compared to traditional letters. Additionally, the domestication of ICT-specific jargon in the novel underscores the relevance of digital language in contemporary literature. The study also demonstrates that IMC represents a modern stylistic approach effectively utilized by Adichie. The insights from this research are significant for students, scholars, and researchers in English, Linguistics, Mass Communication, ICT, and Literature, providing a framework for understanding the interplay between technology and literary creativity.

Keywords: *Internet-mediated communication, ICT, Blogs, E-mails, Digital style*

1. Introduction

The astounding development in Information Communication Technology (ICT) has transformed all fields of human endeavours. The advent of computers has positively affected literature because of the various media that writers employ in their literary texts. The admixtures of internet-mediated language and style result in textual multimodality. Early literary works published by Chinua Achebe, John Pepper Clark, Buchi Emecheta hardly used internet mediated language and style. These authors mostly employed surrogate or drummed language, town-criers, epistolary styles as ways of communicating.

In contemporary time, the language of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) gains momentum in Adichie's Americanah. This shows that Adichie is moving at a great space in her creative

writing by deploying the language of social media in the novel under study. Adichie mostly employs letters, diaries, folktales, drummed language as narrative ploys in *Purple Hibiscus* and *Half of a Yellow Sun*.

However, the domestication of internet-mediated communication media in Adichie's *Americanah* marks the changing phase of literature. *Americanah*, published in 2013, is Adichie's third novel that dwells on the issues of love, maladministration, migration, racism, hair-politics, hardships in America and Europe, feminism, and how to survive abroad.

The domestication of internet-mediated language and style in Adichie's *Americanah* has drastically altered our communication system in the literary world. This change is occasioned by the proliferation of phones and Facebook. Adichie (2013) attests that communication via letter writing is de-emphasised because of the proliferation of cybercafés, mobile phones, and Facebook. Significantly, Adichie has infused internet-mediated style in *Americanah* to advance plots, enhance descriptions of the settings, delineate characters, encourage multimodality and promote distant communication. This study, therefore, examines the style and language of e-mailing, blogging, phoning and text messaging as social media in *Americanah*.

2. Literature review

This section is bifurcated into conceptual and empirical reviews. The conceptual review dwells on the concept of internet, language and style whereas empirical review hinges on the empirical studies on Adichie's *Americanah*.

2.1. Conceptualisation review of the Internet, language, and style

Internet

According to Crystal (2004), the language of cyberspace has many descriptive labels such as mobile messaging, short messaging and mobile messaging. Similarly, Thurlow, Lengel and Tomic (2004: 118) provide cyberspace jargons to include e-talk and netspeak. Downing, Covington, Covington and Covington (2009) assert an internet is a system which forwards messages that connects the network of computer worldwide. Microsoft Computer Dictionary (2002: 281) defines internet as a computer networking system that transmits data from one computer to another. Similarly, A Dictionary of Computing (2008: 259) refers to the word internet as 'the global informal network' that connects 'a very substantial fraction of the world's computer networks.' Comer (2019: 41) states that the internet provides 'digital communication.' Generally speaking, internet transfers files, electronic mails and remote logins. In this study, Internetmediated communication (IMC) is an umbrella term for computer-aided communication. These media of communication can be synchronous and asynchronous. Synchronous communication uses telephone communication and instant messaging to elicit information promptly whereas asynchronous communication uses blogs, e-mails and text messages whose information may not be retrieved on time.

Language and style

Every discipline has its language and style it uses. Special words and expressions that different fields of human endeavours deploy are technically known as registers. Effective manipulation of language and style spice written and oral discourses. In his words, Bussmann (2008) opines that language is a means of

expressing or exchanging of information, concepts, thoughts and knowledge. Crystal (2008: 266) defines language as the form of concrete communication that involves 'speaking, writing or signing.' Aarts, Chalker and Weiner (2014: 230) also look at language as a special human attribute which is used 'for written or spoken communication.' Language is specie-specific and it is this attribute that distinguishes man from other creatures. It is seen as a style of an utterance or a given discourse such as literary, poetic, graphic, euphemistic and epigrammatic languages. It is also viewed as special dictions or registers such as the internet-mediated communication language in Adichie's *Americanah*. Language is spoken, written, signed and surrogated, that is, language has verbal and non-verbal communicative dimensions. It is the stylistic deployment of language that constitutes author's style.

Crystal and Davy (2013) refer to style as an idiolect, entire gamut of the language habits and effectiveness of a mode of expression. According to Wales (2011), style is a manner of expression in writing and speaking; variation in language use; the set of linguistic features; a language; choice and a deviation from linguistic or literary norm. Gibbons and Whiteley (2018: 3) assert that a style shows the relationship that exists between 'linguistic form and literary meaning and interpretation.' Style means various choices and vocabularies that speakers or writers use when they speak or write. The study of style is what is generally known as stylistics. The choice of internet-mediated communication jargons constitutes Adichie's style in *Americanah*.

2.2. Empirical studies on Internet-mediated Language and style in *Americanah*

Yohannes (2012), Maximilian (2014) and Kelvin (2015) examine *Americanah* as a postcolonial novel. Alexander (2013) asserts that Adichie's *Americanah* centres on gender and characters' hybridity or hybridization in America. Kaur (2014) and Khazanovych (2016) identify migration, race, gender and education. Guarracino (2014: 14) affirms that blogging enhances reportage and story narration of Adichie's *Americanah* and it is used as a social commentary. Martin (2015) examines how Westernisation in America is impactful to the people of Africa. Back (2016) enumerates factors that aid in identities' constructions in *Americanah* which include: hair, kin colour and skin colour. Rosha, Kaur and Kumar (2016) state the significance of instant messages and their influence on relevant media use patterns. Toivanen (2016) uses email as a type of asynchronous internet-mediated communication in Adichie's *Americanah* and Tadjó's *Loin de Pere*. Furthermore, Kabore (2016) and Arafath (2017) state that Adichie's *Americanah* hinges on migration and racial discriminations. Begum (2017) avers that the thrust of *Americanah* is on racism and sexism. Leetsch (2017) posits that *Americanah* gives voice to the silenced and oppressed, thus constructing their identities. Hadriana (2017) examines the role that computer-mediated communication has on the students' writing ability and perceptions on CMC application in writing classes.

Mami (2018: 183-4) observes that in *Americanah*, Ifemelu uses blogging style which is an aspect of 'social media' because of an urgent need to express herself globally. According to Mami (2018: 184), Ifemelu uses email to communicate with Wambui, her Kenyan classmate, about the issue of 'race in America.' Wambui therefore encourages her to start a blog so as to air her relevant views that can help her large audience.

Mami notes that the idea of using blog is a reversal of the status quo in the literary scholarship. Derecka (2019) investigates the linguistic potentialities of transphobic discrimination experienced by the internet users. Candrasari (2019) shows the netizens interact with one another and how this interaction occurs within the realm of social media. Dias and Pinto (2019) observe that in order to have a large audience, Efemelu, a protagonist in *Americanah*, launches her blog to discuss effects of racism. Through the sandwiching of blogging style in *Americanah*, Efemelu becomes bold, popular and a mouth-piece for Africans who are hunted in America and Europe. Radwan (2019) deploys blogging style and language to challenge racial discrimination in America.

Aor (2019: 254) affirms that 'Adichie's use of blogging, Short Message Service (SMS) and e-mails indicates the digitalization of literature.' Blog is a widely used social medium in *Americanah*. In Adichie's *Americanah* (2013), Ifemelu writes a blog about the issues of racism in America. Aor (2019: 255) attests that 'the near-absence of epistolary style in *Americanah* is the overkill of blogs.' Ifemelu initiates the use of blogging and other characters join her. Adichie's famous post is shown below:

Hispanic means the frequent companions of American blacks in poverty rankings, Hispanic means a slight step above American blacks in the American ladder, Hispanic means the chocolate-skinned woman from Peru, Hispanic means the indigenous people of Mexico, Hispanic means the biracial-looking folks from the Dominican Republic. Hispanic means the faler folks from Puerto Rico. Hispanic also means the blond, blue-eyed guy from Argentina. All you need to be Spanish-speaking but not from Spain and Voila, you're a race called Hispanic (*Americanah*, 2013: 105).

From the above quote, Aor (2019: 255) attests that 'blog is an effective medium of communication.' Aor (2019: 256) also identifies 'electronic mails (e-mails)' as an instance of social media in *Americanah* and the exchange of e-mail is found in the discussion between Ifemelu and Obinze. This is graphically captured below:

Ceiling, Kedu? Hope all is well with work and family. Ranyinudo said she ran into you some time ago and that you now have a child! Proud Papa. Congratulations. I recently decided to move back to Nigeria. Should be in Lagos in a week. Would love to keep in touch. Take care Ifemelu.

According to Aor (2019: 256), the above e-mail 'illustrates the style of text messages – deviations.' This statement – 'Hope all is well with work and family' – does not have a subject 'I'; 'Should be in Lagos in a week. Would love to keep in touch' do not have the subject 'I' as well. This implies that e-mails have informal and formal language. Estarellas (2021–2022) uses Adichie's *Americanah* to investigate the contribution of blogging has on interactional feminism. As a narrative technique, blogging aids Ifemelu to define her personality by way of shaping her thoughts and putting them down. Asika, Madu and Akabuike (2022) investigate linguistic features employed in *Americanah* and how these features are relevant in the novel.

The above empirical studies centred on the various applications of IMC or CMC in literature and other fields of human endeavours. Guarracino, Mami, Estarellas, Dias and Pinto (2014) discussed the relevance of

blogging as social media, narrative device, a weapon for fighting racial discrimination and feminism in *Americanah*. Toivanen dwelled on the uses of e-mail in Adichie's *Americanah* and Aor employs the language of ICT in Adichie's *Americanah* by examining blogging and e-mails. The above studies only explored Adichie's blogs and e-mails and did not investigate internet-mediated language and style in *Americanah*. This is the gap that this study attempts to fill.

3.3. Computer-mediated Communication (CMC) Theory

According to Holmes (2009: 161), computer-mediated communication (CMC) is that kind of communication which is done through the use of internet. Phoning, blogging, e-mailing and facebooking are said to be mediated by computer if encoder's conversation is conveyed to the decoder digitally. The information conveyed via computer can be recorded digitally and be deciphered by the interlocutors or readers. E-mails, blogs, Facebooks, telephone conversations chat rooms and bulletin boards are all forms of computer-mediated communication and what is mediated is communication.

Computer-mediated Communication is dichotomised in synchronous and asynchronous modes. Synchronous communication is a kind of communication that involves the immediate exchange of information among the interlocutors. Examples of synchronic conversations are instant messaging, telephone conversations and audio and video conferencing. Asynchronous communication is a conversation through internet that does not demand immediate answer or response from the recipient. Examples include emails, blogs, SMS, facebooking, workplace chat, digital whiteboards and meeting whiteboard software.

The deployment of CMC in this study is vitally important because it enhances distant communication among Adichie's characters in *Americanah*. The preponderance utilisation of blogs, telephone conversations and emails serves time and enhances quick narration than when letters and other surrogate communication are used. Furthermore, the adoption of CMC in this study also enables Adichie's character to freely exchange, copy, edit and disseminate information to other characters without much ado. CMC brings about multimodal narrative techniques in this study. Finally, the domestication of CMC in *Americanah* is a clear indication that Information Communication Technology (ICT) is highly significant in literary texts.

4. Methodology

The sampling technique used in this study for data elicitation is judgemental or purposive sampling. The reason for selecting *Americanah* is that it is replete with copious instances of blogs, emails, telephone calls and text messages. Methodologically, this study used *Americanah* as a primary source where data for this study were drawn. The documentary sources were obtained via journal articles, textbooks, dictionaries, encyclopaedias, dissertations and theses that boosted this study's review. As for data presentation and analysis, the author read *Americanah*; selected IM stylistic features; classified them into blogs, e-mails, text messages and telephone conversations and analysed them under internet-mediated style and language.

5. Result and discussion

The thrust of this study is on the internet-mediated style and language in Adichie's *Americanah*. The result of data is based on the research objective whose aim is to 'investigate the aspects of internet-mediated language and style used in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Americanah*.' To that end, the the result of internet-mediated language and style has been discussed under four broad headings:

i. Phoning as internet-mediated language and style in Adichie's *Americanah*, ii. Blogging as internet-mediated language and style in Adichie's *Americanah*, iii. E-mailing as internet-mediated language and style in Adichie's *Americanah*, and iv. Text messaging as internet-mediated language and style in Adichie's *Americanah*

5.1. Discussion

Phoning as an Internet-mediated Language and Style in *Americanah*

Telephone conversation is almost supplanting messengers, envoys, bush burning, drummed and other surrogate communications, especially, in contemporary prose-fictions and dramatic texts. Adichie employs telephone conversation to easy and facilitate communication among her characters. The American returnees converse with one another via phones. In Adichie's (2013) *Americanah*, Ranyinudo affirms that before the advent of internet, they communicate via letters but now they communicate often with the proliferation of cybercafés, telephones and Facebooks.

Telephone conversation is an example of synchronous communication that expresses interpersonal conversations in *Americanah*. Telephone conversations resonate with colloquialisms, vernacularisms and unEnglish or babyish syntax as evident in the conversation between Kosi calls Obinze: 'Darling, kedu ebe i no?' (Adichie, 2013: 21) and Aisha's response: 'Sorry, I make quick call' (Adichie, 2013: 39). The former is expressed in Igbo and the latter omits auxiliary verb 'will' or 'shall.'

Telephone conversions also give information about Adichie's characters. As the General notices that he cannot visit Aunt Uju, he tells her that he will not come. Upon discovering that she takes in, Ifemelu converses with Aunt Uju on the phone. Ifemelu says she takes in and it is once that she eats the food a week ago (Adichie, 2003). Ifemelu's conversation is highly coded; she does not want to state that she is pregnant. Again, Ifemelu seldom calls Obinze because she does not want to waste her recharge card (Adichie, 2013). Aunt Uju speaks for a long time on the phone with emotion-laden voice because of the problems she faced in America (Adichie, 2013).

Furthermore, phone conversations are used for inquires, requests, reports and apologies. Dike inquires when Ifemelu will come to America and wishes her to come and take care of him. Dike does not want to go to Miss Brown because of her stinky bathroom (Adichie, 2013). Aunt Uju called Ifemelu: "Ifem, kedu? Aunt Uju said. "Fine." Aunt Uju asks Ifemelu if she finds a job and also tells her that Mr Brown reports that Dike and a girl in the third grade 'were showing each other their private parts' (Adichie, 2013: 141). The restaurant manager apologises through phone call, tells Ngozi (Ifemelu) that she is sorry and that she decides to employ a more competent person (Adichie, 2013). Again, Ginika tells Ifemelu on the phone that

Kimberly has recruited another person for the job she applied for but she will keep her in mind (Adichie, 2013).

Phone conversations are main means through which reports and information are conveyed. Elena yells at Ifemelu because Ifemelu wants to slap her. (Adichie, 2013). Out of desperation, Ifemelu calls the tennis coach at Ardmore, asks him when she will start working. She suggests that she will come at once (Adichie, 2013). After visiting the coach, Ifemelu tells Aunty Uju on the phone that she goes to work and the man pays her a hundred dollars (Adichie, 2013). Aunty Uju replies that she should look for something permanent. Through phone style, dialogue is enhanced and the speeches of characters are analysed according to their linguistic, economic and social factors.

Generally, phone style is a phatic communion that is shared by the interlocutors. Ifemelu's mother asks after her daughter's welfare and expects her to send something to her. She uses simple sentences so that her message will be easily delivered and understood and also to avoid ambiguity. Obinze calls and tells Ifemelu that he loves her (Adichie, 2013). Ginika also phones Ifemelu and enquires how she is faring and she says she is okay. Ginika discovers that Ifemelu is behaving strangely and that she refuses to pick Obinze's calls (Adichie, 2013). Through phone conversation, we know characters who are caring and those that are enemies.

Phone style also reveals what the characters do, where they live, what they intend to do in Americanah. Ifemelu talks with Aunty Uju and Dike on the phone and Dike tells her that he scores great goals (Adichie, 2013). Also, Ifemelu's mother relates to her daughter how the family is faring at home, that is, her father gets a job, buys a phone and a tyre (Adichie, 2013). Cleotilde tells Obinze on the phone that she has been in London for the past six years (Adichie, 2013). Obinze's mother tells him on the phone that she will receive him in Lagos when he comes back from London (Adichie, 2013). Phone conversation is only restricted to characters who have the contacts of other characters and that their problems, welfares, desires and top secrets are shared among themselves. Phone style is fast, foregrounds the emotions of the characters, measures characters' linguistic competencies, is colloquial or chatty and uses conversational registers.

Blogging as an Internet-mediated Language and Style in Americanah.

Another important IM language and style in Americanah is blogging style. According to Baron (2008), Jorn Barger coined the word blog in 1997. Microsoft Computer Dictionary (2002: 563) defines a blog as a website that regularly updates contents that reflect the 'interests of the site's host.' Furthermore, Daintith and Wright (2008) see blog as a journal that is publicly accessed on the web and maintained by individuals or groups. Downing, Covington, Covington and Covington (2009: 58 – 9) opine that blog or 'weblog' is a kind of 'personal column posted on the internet.' Similarly, Danesi (2009: 44) asserts that blog is a 'website with a regularly updated list of commentary' that hooks 'information on the internet.' Fini (2009: 714) maintains that the term blog is the blend of 'web log.' Blogs are personal diaries or news journals that have titles, texts and links. The language used in writing blogs is generally informal. The deployment of blogging style in Americanah can thus become Adichie's linguistic and literary identity, according to Granieri (2005).

Richards and Schmidt (2010: 59), blogs enhances conversation between 'the writer and reader'. Yus (2011: 95) asserts that blogs perform tremendous roles that enhance 'a mutual manifestness of information.' In addition, Yus (2011: 96) maintains that blogs have 'verbal-visual' components that indicate the communicative and informative intentions of the blogger.

Adichie employs blogs as an invaluable weapon for fighting racism, oppression, gender inequality and dissemination of information. In Adichie's (2013) *Americanah*, Ifemelu complains that blogs are new and unfamiliar to her but she chooses blogs because she desires to have other listeners to converse with them. Ifemelu starts blogging after she breaks up with Curt and her blogging (Adichie, 2013). Ifemelu therefore names her blog 'Raceteenth' (Adichie, 2013: 292) and the first post she sends is entitled 'The Hot White Ex.' Ifemelu employs blogging style to vent her anger on her ex-boy friend. She therefore uses this medium to critically discuss the evil effects of racism in America. Ifemelu employs the above excerpt to state that there is no love lost between American Blacks and American Whites. Ifemelu is exceedingly happy for the impact her blog has started yielding as the number of her readers has increased tremendously (Adichie, 2013).

Blog posts are stylistically marked in *Americanah*. They all have quoted titles; written in a different font types and emboldened; content words are capitalised; discussed racism and perform social functions. In a racist nation such as America, the richness of the black is not recognized because he is not an American. The language of blogs also contains fragmentary statements. This indicates that blogs have informal language and style. One of Ifemelu blog posts shows social stratification within the Non-American Black in America.

The capitalisation of some blog posts indicates loudness, prominence, aesthetics and memorability. Undoubtedly, Ifemelu is a 'leading blogger' (Adichie, 2013: 305) about race in *Americanah*.

Apart from Ifemelu's *Raceteenth*, there is *HappilyKinkyNappy.com*, that 'had a bright yellow background, message boards full of posts, thumbnail photos of black women blinking at the top' (Adichie, 2013: 212). The graphological stylistic features of *HappilyKinkyNappy.com* have been foregrounded for aesthetic appeals. The title of the blog has three words and each word is written with initial capital, followed by small letters, a dot [.] and ended with com. As far as Kurt, a character in *Americanah*, is concerned blogs are weapons for fighting racism and encouraging feminist movement or ideology in America. Again, blogs use unconventional spelling or eye-dialect as reflected in the spelling of 'sistas' (Adichie, 2013: 231). The spelling is stylistically significant because it represents how the character pronounces 'sisters.' Blog titles and accounts have letters and figures as in *Jamilah1977*.

Ifemelu starts another blog when she comes back to Nigeria. The title of her blog is: *The Small Redemptions of Lagos* (Adichie, 2013: 418). It has a design which has blue and white colours and picture of Lagos scenes appears on the masthead (Adichie, 2013). Ifemelu intends to publish articles about health care, Nigropolitain Club and fashion and her first post is an interview she has with Priye. Her post about

Nigerpolitan Club attracted many comments and ‘the blog had one thousand unique visitors’ (Adichie, 2013: 422).

Blogs are used in Americanah as a source of advertising products. Ifemelu advertises products such as ‘hair butters, boutique, Pantene shampoos and Covergirl make-up’ (Adichie, 2013: 303). Furthermore, blogs serve as a tool for teaching or interacting with people. Director of multicultural life at Connecticut asks Ifemelu to talk to the students (Adichie, 2013). The didactic function of blogs comes from the e-mail that a corporation in Pennsylvania sends to Ifemelu that invites her to be a lead presenter at their annual workshop because she is a blogger. Blogs provide entertainment and income. Ifemelu is also featured in a show and she is named “The Blogger” (Adichie, 2013: 304). Ifemelu speaks at events on different media outlets for entertainment and pecuniary reasons. She has an opportunity to converse with a blogger who specialises in make-ups (Adichie, 2013).

Electronic mailing (e-mailing) as an Internet-mediated Language and Style in Americanah.

From time immemorial, epistolary style was used by renowned writers such as William Shakespeare, Fyodor Dostoevsky, Bram Stoker, Thornton Wilder, Stephen King, Bob Randall, Samuel Richardson, Alice Walker and Richard Wright as a narrative technique in their literary works (prose-fictions and dramatic texts). With the advent of ICT, the use of letters is gradually giving way to e-mails as evident in Adichie’s Americanah. Microsoft Computer Dictionary (2002) asserts that electronic mail transfers messages and files over a communications’ network. Similarly, Downing, Covington, Covington and Covington (2009: 165) defines electronic mail as transmitting messages via ‘computer from one person to another.’ Chan (2012: 10) affirms that e-mail is it is ‘quick and easy.’ In his words, Crystal (2004) asserts that e-mail uses of computer systems to transmit messages between interlocutors. The language of e-mail should be active, precise and plain that communicates effectively. E-mailing style allows characters to express their thoughts or feelings without authorial intrusion and this brings about the element of verisimilitude in the story.

E-mailing is a asynchronous communication whose messages are timed. That is why Ifemelu sends an email doubting whether Obinze will respond but he later does (Adichie, 2013). Additionally, Ifemelu composes and sends Obinze an e-mail without re-reading it. Ifemelu tells Obinze that she returns to Nigeria and Obinze later thanks and wishes her well (Adichie, 2013). E-mails are media through which assignments are submitted in America (Adichie, 2013). E-mails are private messages that are exchanged between two characters. Obinze tells Ifemelu in his first e-mail that the opening of cybercafés in Nsukka has facilitated the transmission of information via e-mails. The opening of cybercafé in Nsukka enables Obinze to use emails as a medium of correspondence. Ifemelu’s e-mail to Obinze shows that she wants to apologise for not receiving Obinze’s calls and that he should bury the hatchet. She concludes that she misses Obinze a lot. Ifemelu reads the e-mail that Curt’s lover writes to Curt and her address is SparklingPaola123. The deployment of e-mails creates familiarity and enhances conversational style.

Text messaging as an Internet-mediated Language and Style in Americanah.

Most of the composed text messages in Americanah are sent as e-mails only few are sent as texts. Text messages are asynchronous in nature. Ifemelu writes Dike a text but he 'had still not replied to her text' (Adichie, 2013: 15). Ifemelu sends a text to Wambui that she detests her hair and she does not go to work today. Wambui replies that Ifemelu should access HappilyKinkyNappy.com which is a natural hair community (Adichie, 2013). Blaine sends Ifemelu a text if she hears about Mr White who works in the library. Ifemelu replies Blaine back by saying she has not heard from him. These texts save time, reduce risks of travelling to deliver them and are privately delivered.

Americanah is laced with the style and language of ICT because of the advancement in technology. The style in IMC in Adichie's Americanah was discussed under phoning, blogging, e-mailing and text messaging. Thurlow, Lengel and Tomic (2004: 125) identify online chats, instant messaging or text messaging as the best place to see 'the language of conversation on the internet.' They list some common typographic features employed to achieve this interactional style including: letters used as homophones, sophisticated punctuations, capitalisation or symbols for stress and emphasis, stylized spelling, direct requests, interactional indicators, more elaborate programming, coloured text, emotes and other graphic symbols. Adichie's Americanah contains most of the identifiable stylistic features. Generally, the IM language found in Americanah is colloquial, fragmentary, deviated, prosaic, mixed with standard and babyish syntax, full of quotations and is stylistically marked.

6. Conclusion

Internet-mediated language or style is a strand of CMC which is used in literary studies and it has started replacing the traditional narrative media such as letters, diaries and surrogate language. This clearly demonstrates that IM language/style has brought about literary renaissance. Internet-mediated style has added new vocabularies to the literary texts and it connects cyber studies with linguistics and literature. The study also foregrounds the roles of IM language and style in Americanah. The deployment of IM language/style in the literary texts has result in multimodality, verisimilitude, conversational style and measured characters' linguistic competence. IMC serves time and quickens narration of events, advancement of plot and facilitating mutual communication among characters. The domestication of IM jargons in Americanah also foregrounds the language of ICT in literature. The following recommendations have been made:

- i. This study will have tremendous impacts on English Language, Linguistics and Literature students and researchers that may wish to investigate the relevance of multimedia and cyber studies.
- ii. Furthermore, scholars and lecturers will also use this study to analyse the language of ICT in Stylistics and Sociolinguistics.
- iii. Mass Communication, ICT and Computer Science scholars will use this study as reference material as well.
- iv. This study is inexhaustible therefore more studies will be done on other aspects of IM language and style such as Facebook, YouTube, Skype, video conference and webinar.

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